

****Request for Legal Counsel - AI Safety Whistleblower, Good-Faith Disclosure Dismissed, Federal Non-Response**

From: Haley Pedersen <info@eff.org>

To:

Date: 4/10/26 3:01 PM

Hello,

Thank you for reaching out to us at the Electronic Frontier Foundation (EFF) to report this. Apologies, but we don't have capacity to directly advise you on this matter. As a small, grassroots legal advocacy non-profit, EFF is dedicated to defending civil liberties and constitutional rights in the digital world. We focus our limited resources on impact litigation at the federal level, typically addressing novel legal questions or concepts that have not been addressed by the courts. Consequently, our mission is narrowly defined, and we are not equipped to handle all issues beyond this scope.

We suggest you try reaching out to organizations who focus primarily on AI issues. You might start with Partnership on AI: <https://partnershiponai.org/>

We're sorry we cannot offer direct assistance in this matter and wish you the best of luck in resolving your situation.

Best regards,

Haley

Legal Intake Coordinator
(415) 436-9333, Ext. 159
info@eff.org

Become a Member! <https://www.eff.org/support>

On Wed, 08 Apr 2026, synthetic.neurosciene56@protonmail.com wrote:

> Dear EFF legal team,

>

> I'm reaching out again as I have not received a response regarding my
> prior email. In the time since my last email my research corpus on zenodo
> has grown to 28 records with over 4k cumulative views and an 82% download
> rate which in the niche ai alignment and safety field is "viral". I have
> also uploaded the letters sent to relevant congressional committees along
> with approximately 10gb of Proof of Concept videos with delivery receipts.
> I will be posting this email as well to support transparency and my
> efforts at full disclosure

>

> If you have no interest in this or do not find my situation as meeting
> your mission statement I respectfully request that you please inform me as
> I have spent over 6 months trying to report these grave vulnerabilities
> with no substantive contact and their continued exploitability in critical
> infrastructure, defense and healthcare industries.

>

> The disclosure record is here:
> <https://zenodo.org/records/19444222>

>

> Jesse Luke

>

> Sent from Proton Mail for Android.

>

> <https://zenodo.org/records/19444222>

>

> Sent from [Proton Mail](https://proton.me/mail/home) for Android.

>

> ----- Original Message -----

> On Monday, 01/19/26 at 16:26 synthetic.neurosciene56@protonmail.com wrote:

> >
> > Sent from [Proton Mail](<https://proton.me/mail/home>) for Android.